

YES-Europe

2018 Annual Conference Report

YES
Europe

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The right idea, the right persons, the right moment

History is full of instances of breakthrough advances appearing unexpectedly, by the elusive combination of preparation, luck and means. Never before has humanity had access to such an amount of information and knowledge. Almost anyone can delve into anything. It is easy though to drown in such an ocean. Knowing what is relevant, when the right time is and how to exploit it are the new challenges.

In this context, incumbent firms tend to rely only on familiar channels and strategies. However, the challenges arising are anything but familiar. Only through a determined effort towards diversity and inclusion, defying all biases (age, origin, professional background, gender) can the energy sector be sure to gather all the transformative potential it needs.

This is our mission at YES-Europe (Young leaders in Energy and Sustainability). We organize Annual Conferences to bring together a diverse community of young professionals and students. We give them the opportunity to speak, to debate, to bond, and to access leading experts.

For the third edition of our Annual Conferences, the challenge was to maintain a friendly environment while the number and diversity of participants continued to increase. To achieve it, we encouraged participants to connect whether in the thematic tables at lunch, the country presentations, the pitch contest or the poster session. The participants got to know each other and learned about their different backgrounds. It makes us happy to learn about projects getting started thanks to meetings during our conference.

Our deepest thanks to the direction of the UPM Energy and Mining School and all its personnel, which did far more we ever dared to expect. We are indebted to the industry leaders who shared their expertise, to the volunteers who gave us their time and to the attendees who trusted us one more year. Thanks to Carlos Hernández Hernández, whose brave leadership and devotion to YES-Europe made possible the conference. On behalf of the YES-Europe Team, we thank you for helping us build the world of tomorrow.

YES-Europe Team

The Idea behind YES-Europe

Our Vision

The YES-Europe network is a one-of-a-kind organization that brings together a community of nearly 1,000 young professionals and students in energy across Europe. We envision a world that works together to achieve sustainable, accessible, and secure energy.

Our Challenge

YES works to break up the silos in the energy industry. We believe it is impoverishing that nuclear or oil professionals, energy lawyers, or policy consultants are locked in their own online discussions, conferences, and websites. This social structure favors local, narrow solutions to problems that are systemic. Moreover, the silo mindset permeates younger generations and perpetuates itself. This issue leads to slower and inferior solution generations. We decided to change this.

Our Strategy

YES-Europe builds stronger online and in-person communities of next generation leaders across energy disciplines, sectors, and countries. We believe the best way to solve complex energy challenges is together.

To accomplish this goal, we are building strong country-level networks with our Country Representatives model. The national hubs connect existing local stakeholders and develop online and in-person communication channels. Strong national networks allow us to build a strong European, and later, global network.

In addition, we conduct our cornerstone event - the Annual Conference that brings together representatives from across Europe for two days in a single city.

YES-Europe also conducts in-house analytics about the needs and opinions of our members about the future of energy, which we share with broader stakeholders to influence their decision-making.

We are also developing an integrative online platform. It will allow our members to efficiently find opportunities such as jobs, events or grants and connect with each other to share knowledge and connections.

YES-Europe is growing

YES-Europe grows steadily since its inception. It is one of YES key priorities – to increase its network of young professionals and students in energy and sustainability. The recent expansion into Finland and the Netherlands proves our commitment to growth.

The Netherlands' already have an exhaustive energy network. This enables YES to tap into it and connect members with the existing opportunities and knowledge. Finland is our entry to the group of Scandinavian countries, leaders in the energy and sustainability areas. These additions multiply our potential reach!

With Country Representatives in 10 different countries now, the YES network is growing at a rapid pace. Something unique about YES network is that the countries spread across Europe – it is not just the neighboring countries in Western Europe (Germany, the Netherlands, Switzerland, Italy and Spain) but also the UK, Finland, and eastern countries of Russia, Poland and Moldova. This contributes to accomplishing our mission to bring young people together to work on the complex issue of sustainable energy.

Regional boundaries fade when people look at a genuine problem together. We have the ability to put aside our biases and work together for something much greater than ourselves: preserving our home, the Earth, while providing sufficient, reliable energy at affordable costs.

#YESMadrid2018 Conference in Numbers

The 3rd Annual Conference in Madrid drew together 80 people from 12 countries, including: Spain, Germany, Italy, Russia, UK, Moldova, Switzerland, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Russia, Sweden, and France. The backgrounds of our participants ranged from engineering to law, business, entrepreneurship, and international relations.

The 2018 YES-Europe AC was a unique opportunity for a Russian oil and gas student to debate how they see the future of energy supply with another young professional from the Netherlands whose primary focus through his education has been renewables energy.

Figure 1. Countries of residence of attendants to YES Europe 2018 Annual Conference in Madrid, Spain.

Time for networking

One of the most exciting aspects of bringing together energy students and young professionals is the opportunity to meet in-person and get to know each other's perspectives, stories, dreams and goals.

Events are a great way for making connections, but how effective are they, actually? Many events just hope for people to randomly bump into the people they want to meet. We decided to change this. We have introduced tools and sessions that bring people together who had indicated their interest in a common topic.

One of our tools was [EpicEvents](#). EpicEvents is a conference app that not only has the conference agenda and live-updates stream but also allows participants to create a profile, browse other participants' profiles and interests, and make purposeful connections.

Another approach we used to match people was surveying. We asked them at registration what are the top three things they are looking for and what are the top three things they can offer others. Sending emails to complementary or similarly interested individuals, we encouraged them to meet during the event.

Besides these, we also set up opportunities for one-to-many communication sessions, including one poster session, one pitch session, and country presentations. In these sessions, people shared their interests with a larger audience to spark ideas for follow-up discussions during a coffee break or at the evening social event.

In order to keep improving, we analyze the results of our efforts according to the experiences of the participants.

Figure 2 The agenda and attendees of the YES-Europe 2018 Annual Conference on the EpicEvents App.

Figure 3 Stated preferences about how to make new connections.

Participants met an average of 30 people. About four of these connections led to opportunities for immediate, specific collaborations. Between five and six connections could lead to a direct collaboration in the near future. Finally, a bit less than half the connections, 13 on average, were connections with people the participants see themselves keeping in touch with thanks to a common interest.

Figure 4 Average number of connections according to relevance for establishing a collaboration and by means of connection.

The meeting strategy that led to a larger number of connections was “other means” - people meeting each other, informally in their own time, at coffee breaks or over drinks in the evening, followed by thematic lunches. However, bringing the most connections does not always mean providing also the most relevant ones. Pre-matched and connections via Epic Events were less frequent, but more relevant. Four out of five of those connections were seen as conducive to an immediate or near-term collaboration.

#YESMadrid2018

Stories from the conference

The YES-Europe team is happy to show you how great the YES-Europe 2018 Annual Conference was. We cannot wait to meet you in the next one!

Get off on the right foot (Day 1)

Ekaterina Paramonova, Co-lead of YES-Europe who presented the developments of YES-Europe to the audience, gave a first welcome to the participants. The welcome keynote delivered by Prof. **Alberto Ramos Millán**, Professor Energy and Fuels department and Director of Gomez Pardo foundation, followed it.

Figure 5. Keynote presentation by Diego Díaz Pilas, Head of New Ventures and Technology Prospects at Iberdrola.

The keynote presentation was delivered by **Diego Díaz Pilas**, Head of new ventures and technology prospects, Iberdrola. In his talk, he highlighted the current state of innovation in the energy sector and how new technologies are driving the energy transition. The panel discussion that followed blended legal, technical and business perspective together so as to examine the role on new technologies such as Artificial Intelligence, Big data and Blockchain in the energy transition.

It followed an informative presentation by **Jose Ignacio Botello Martinez**, Energy & Climate manager at Repsol. His talk delved into the Oil and Gas Climate Initiative (OGCI) and shed light on the climate friendly practices adopted in the oil and gas industry.

Figure 6 Arrecife start-up co-founders present their company to the participants.

In the afternoon, the YES-Europe country delegations presented a summary of the current state of the energy industry in their country.

The Solar energy industry plays a major role in the Spanish energy sector according to **Prof. Vincente Salas Merino**, Associate Professor and Director of the PV systems unit at UC3M. He shared his insights on the current challenges faced by the solar energy industry, highlighting how innovation plays a major role in overcoming these challenges.

Figure 7 YES-Europe team from Italy.

It was time for the interactive sessions: the business simulation game and the start-up ideation bootcamp (see more details in their sections below). Finally, the first day concluded with a poster session and apero where the participants displayed their research, projects and other ideas with their peers.

Figure 8 One of the participants explains her research to other attendees during the poster session.

Taking an active role (Day 2)

In the morning session, **Olalla del Rio Barrio**, Secretary General of the World Energy Council Spain, shared a sneak preview of the World Energy Issues Monitor 2018: “Key trends in energy innovation.”

The World Energy Issues Monitor 2018 surveyed over 1,000 people worldwide to identify and rank the top issues in the energy sector. A similar presentation can be seen [here](#) and a news article of the report [here](#) (Spanish).

The talk was followed by a series of presentations around advanced grid management techniques and electromobility. **Dr. Pablo Frias Marin**, Deputy Director of IIT, talked about advancements in electromobility, focusing in particular on its opportunities for providing storage capacity for grid storage.

Figure 9 Olalla del Rio Barrio, Secretary General of the WEC Spain, interacts with one of the participants after her presentation.

Figure 10 Jose Ignacio Botello Martinez, Energy & Climate manager at Repsol, talks about the Oil and Gas Climate Initiative (OGCI) (day 1).

Afterwards, **Professor Gregorio Lopez**, Assistant Professor at UPM, piqued the interest of the participants in smart cities and smart grids.

Laura Garcia Chiquero, Corporate Strategy and M&A at CEPSA then joined for a panel discussion, presenting ideas for advanced mobility concepts.

The day included the now-traditional pitch contest. Participants from countries like Italy, the UK, Switzerland, Moldova or Russia presented their recent research or work during 5 minutes. The winner of the 2018 edition was **Elena Rybkina**, student at the Moscow State Institute of International Relations (MGIMO).

Five key trends of Russian energy sector

By *Elena Rybkina*

The large size of Russian territory having only a 3.3% less surface area than Pluto, can easily explain the importance of this country in the energy market, with its vast amount of natural resources. The structure of the Russian energy sector is extensively discussed among energy experts worldwide, as a great amount of energy sources are exported and are of fundamental importance for both European and Asian countries.

Contact Elena and learn more about her work:

e.rybkina@bcmgimo.com

[LinkedIn](#)

Several trends of the Russian energy scene have been investigated. Here are the five most important ones. (1) The raise of LNG production and sale on the external market, (2) the diversification of the Arctic energy sources, (3) the development of distributed electricity, (4) the substitution of uranium with thorium in the nuclear energy sector, and (5) the increase of energy efficiency, especially in terms of separate households. These trends were identified according to specific criteria (relevance in the market and innovative perspective).

All the trends have an essential influence on the energy sector and have been on the Russian market for a time period of at least 10 years, thus affecting significantly the level and structure of demand and supply. Last, but not least

Figure 11 Members of YES-Europe team present at the #YESMadrid2018 conference.

Be the leading actor: Business simulation game

Motivation

The Business Simulation Game is one of the main parts of the Annual Conference. In the previous two conferences, one game simulated climate change negotiation between countries and industry lobbies and another game mirrored stakeholder consultations for policy making about the support of alternative primary energy sources in a European country. This year as well, students were given the task to simulate the process of trying to influence an energy committee decision-making. The game aimed to encourage the participants to think at a global scale and find creative solutions within a limited time. Another goal was to motivate students to think out of the box, to interact with each other and to use their analytical abilities and soft skills at the maximum level.

The Game

The game simulated the process that Italy's energy council would have to go through in order to assess the energy strategy until 2030, deciding which energy source should be financed for the future and by how much. The Chamber of ministers had a budget of 20 billion euros, sum that had to be distributed among the different industries according to the proposals submitted by each one of them. Students were randomly divided into eleven teams of 4-8 people representing one of the following industries:

- Electric vehicles industry
- Automobile industry
- Natural gas industry
- Oil industry
- Solar industry
- Wind industry
- Geothermal industry
- Nuclear fusion
- Hydropower industry
- Energy storage
- Surprise group

To get closer to real conditions, targets and policies were stated: a 40% reduction of greenhouse gases emissions relative to 1990 by 2030, at least a 27% share of final electricity consumption provided by renewable energies, and a 27% energy consumption reduction compared to the business-as-usual scenario.

To guide teams and to provide them with a clear understanding of what they should do in the framework of the game, we listed some guiding questions about what they needed to cover in their proposed strategies. The core question was 'What EU 2030 goals is your strategy helping to achieve and by how much?' Other questions were related to the required budget share, job support, timeline planning and explanations about why Italy's government should invest in their strategy.

To put students out of their comfort zones, and to force them to take faster decisions, the duration of the game was limited to 2.5 hours: 50 minutes for building up the draft of their strategy, 25 minutes for negotiation with jurors (cabinet members), 3 minutes per team for the strategy presentation, and 15 minutes for finalizing and result submission.

Figure 12 Participants debating their strategy for the nuclear industry.

Insights

Besides the final data that resulted from the game, what was astonishing was how close to reality things were. Some groups went through the game all by themselves, while others decided to collaborate and even to present joined proposals. It was a surprise to see how teams interact with each other, industries mix and match, and how members share responsibilities.

Finally, the ministers decided the share that each group would have taken according to the exposition that was made, by the transparency of the request and, of course, by the submitted proposals. Almost every group got less than what they asked, while just two groups managed to get the full amount of the requested money. The significant part of investments was assigned to the alliance of Energy storage, Photovoltaics, and Electric vehicles – this collaboration got 6 billion euros. According to the jurors' decision, the strategy from Wind industry team was also very perspective in the framework of the game rules and aims; the group got 4 billion. Other 50% of the budget was distributed more or less equally among other teams.

The most important lesson from this business game was not to make teams to compete with each other but to encourage participants to find new connections between energy sectors and to learn how to make our world a better place. Even results showed that cooperation leads to the breakthrough.

From ideas to actions: Start-up ideation bootcamp

Motivation

Innovation was at the center point of this year's conference. Keeping in mind YES-Europe's commitment to nurture innovation and provide necessary tools to the future energy leaders for solving the energy challenges, we decided to include an interactive and participative workshop in this year's agenda.

Innovation starts with an idea, but turning that idea into reality is the biggest challenge. However, structuring and focusing the ideation process can be of great help. For this, we decided to use the [Adobe kickbox](#), an open-source tool with this precise scope. The aim of the bootcamp was to initiate the participants to a well-structured process, so that they would be able to iterate on their ideas afterwards.

Figure 13 Team discussing their ideas during the start-up bootcamp.

Bootcamp

The first level, **Inception**, takes the participants back to a very fundamental question: why to innovate? The participants have to explore their minds to derive the true motivation behind their need for innovation. To stimulate their thinking, they are provided with pre-designed cards with some common motivations.

Once the participants connect with their true motivation, the second level delves deep into the **ideation** process.

Considering the requirements of our participants, we chose the following exercises from the Kickbox process: Table of strategic elements, Critical evaluation of new ideas, Question the question, Solo Storming, Writing down ideas - Collecting more ideas, and Brainstorming. Differently from the Adobe methodology, the exercises proposed were combined in two groups of three exercises each.

The first one consisted in the creation of a table of strategic elements: the participants were provided with a sample from the Adobe kickbox kit and had to create a post-it note stack on a wall and write down the secondary or supportive ideas related to their main idea in one column. A different space was provided to stack distracting ideas post-it (e.g. "get the dry cleaning. Pick up Sally from school at 3.") to *clear the mental stack* from other distractions. Participants were asked to first evaluate their own idea and then evaluate the ideas of other fellow participants and ask them to question the questions. To give them some time to reflect on the feedback received from their fellow participants we asked to do solostorming and collect their thoughts into the "Bad ideas notebook", received as a part of their Kickbox kit. A quick brainstorming followed, in order to refine and validate all the ideas developed so far.

The third level focused on **improvement and refinement**: an exercise called "Zen statement" was performed, aimed at developing a way to convey ideas in a clear and effective way. To conclude, the participants were given the remaining material for the last three levels of the Kickbox kit and were encouraged to complete the following steps on their own and share the experience with us in the next conference!

Figure 14 Team of participants presenting their idea.

Conclusions & Next Steps for YES-Europe

The Annual Conference is the time when all of the YES-Europe leadership team members have to meet in-person, reflect on the past year's success for YES, and brainstorm strategy. This year, we recalibrated YES-Europe's vision, mission, and "why" statement. As our mission is to build the European energy community via in-person and online channels, we have decided to make the top priority for the 2018-2019 year to build a YES-Europe online platform.

The aim of this platform is to allow our members and partners to engage with each other and find opportunities at any time, from anywhere. The platform will allow members to find and connect with each other to answer questions like *"I'm currently studying in Switzerland and am looking to move to Germany and work in energy policy. Where do I even start?"* The platform will also provide personalized search opportunities for our members who are looking for jobs, or internships, project opportunities, other conferences, grants or, summer schools. There exist many websites with this purpose, but most of them provide a huge listing of impersonal opportunities, thus reducing their effectiveness.

The Country Representatives and their country teams will continue building strong national networks via in-person events and projects. Their work provides the foundation to what YES-Europe does - strong national networks are essential for building a European network. Having seen the sustained enthusiasm from the attendees of our Annual Conferences over the last three years, we have also confirmed to continue with the Annual Conferences as a keystone event for bringing together our entire European community.

Drumroll please... we are thrilled to announce the 2019 YES-Europe Annual Conference (AC) will take place in the Netherlands Spring 2019. Stay tuned for more information about the dates and other details. **Let's make the fourth one a hit!**

Figure 15 Participants of the YES Europe 2018 Annual Conference in Madrid, Spain.

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You will also receive our monthly newsletter packed with information about YES-Europe and other relevant energy events, job opportunities, analytical surveys and their results, network updates, and much more. Go to our website: www.yes-energy-europe.com

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Shubham Bansal, Data Scientist at Discovergy GmbH
Vincente Salas, Associate Professor and Director of PV systems unit at UC3M

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